

RESIDUAL FLEXURAL STRENGTH AFTER IMPACT AND HYDROSTATIC CYCLING IN GLASS/SYNTACTIC FOAM SANDWICH LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The specific properties of composite materials have led to their increasing use in a number of industries. Their high production cost originally limited their use in specific application areas, namely aerospace, civil and military. However due to the strength and weight advantages that emerge from the use of composite materials, applications have been extended in many engineering fields such as automobile, naval, marine, construction etc. hence reducing their production cost. As a result, traditional tests that have been used for the certification of composite materials in aerospace industry (e.g. compression after impact) need to be re-evaluated and adjusted to the specific needs of other industries.

This work focuses on the investigation of the residual flexural strength after impact behaviour and hydrostatic cycling of sandwich laminates made of woven glass fibre/epoxy resin skin and syntactic foam. An initial finite element analysis was first performed in order to estimate the optimum skin to foam thickness ratio for the highest flexural strength. Samples at different thicknesses were tested under impact at different energy levels and their flexural strength before and after impact were evaluated with a three point bending test. In addition, samples were tested under hydrostatic cycling and their residual flexural strength was investigated with a three point bending test. All tests followed test parameters that are representative of the use of composite materials in subsea engineering structures. The failure modes after each test were further assessed.

1 INTRODUCTION

As the requirement for achieving higher subsea depths is increasing so does the demand for the use of lightweight, high performance materials, such as composite materials, in an effort to replace the traditionally employed metallic structures. The move towards investigation and development of composite materials for deep-water subsea applications can minimise the structural weight which can be difficult and costly to accommodate at high water depths. In addition, the remarkably high properties and strength of composite materials can offer a structural alternative for the design of a number of structures such as remotely operated vehicles.

Composite sandwich structures are a good candidate for offshore subsea engineering for a number of applications. The combination of the thick core and thin skin can achieve high shear stiffness to weight ratios and bending stiffness to weight ratios compared to equivalent homogeneous plates made of the constituent materials only [1]. A number of studies have focused on the dynamic behaviour of sandwich composites and more specifically on low velocity impact [2, 3]. Common failure modes have been identified as core indentation and cracking, core shear, skin buckling and delamination, core-skin debonding and perforation [4, 5]. Bending properties of composite sandwiches have been investigated from a number of researchers outlining the primary failure mechanisms. Collapse mechanism maps have been developed in order to demonstrate the failure modes that take place when sandwich beams are subject to bending stresses. These maps show that the failure mechanisms depend on the geometry of the beam and the relative strength of the core and the skin [6].

Syntactic foams are hollow particle-filled polymers which can be made of polymer, metal or ceramic materials [7]. In a similar way the matrix can be chosen from a variety of available materials.

The syntactic foams exhibit high compressive properties and water absorption resistance [8, 9] which make them very efficient for underwater applications. Three and four point bending tests have been previously employed to study the flexural properties of syntactic foams. Results showed that a combination of failure mechanisms take place, namely fracture features of tensile, compression and shear failure zones [10].

Syntactic foams have been relatively recently used as core materials in sandwich constructions. The skin can be directly laminated on the core and if the same resin is used as the one used for the foam, then skins can act as an integral part of the structure [11]. The compressive properties of syntactic foam core sandwich composites have been studied, in which specimens were subjected to edgewise and flatwise compression testing [12]. In addition the flexural properties of sandwich laminates made of syntactic foam have also been studied where the specimens were subjected to three point bending and shear tests [13].

One of the primary design considerations for underwater offshore engineering applications is the post impact residual strength. In addition to that, many subsea structures are subject to hydrostatic pressure cycling loads, as part of their operation at a range of sea water depths. A representative example is the remotely operated underwater vehicle (ROV). It is therefore critical to ensure that after the structure exposed to hydrostatic loads, its residual strength is still within acceptable range to withstand typical operational loads. One of the most critical operational loads is bending loading. It was therefore decided as part of this work to study the residual bending strength after impact and hydrostatic testing of composite sandwich structures. Although a lot of previous work was focused on the compressive residual properties of composite materials under impact loading which is a primary requirement for aerospace industry, little work has been reported on composite applications for offshore engineering applications. This would involve the study of the residual bending strength after impact and hydrostatic pressure loading [14, 15].

The purpose of the current work has been the investigation of the residual bending properties of composite sandwich laminates made of syntactic foams and E-glass skin after impact testing and hydrostatic pressure cycling. The syntactic foam was made of epoxy resin and glass microspheres and it was rated to withstand ocean depths equivalent to 2,000 metres depth. The E-glass fabric used for the laminates was plain twill weave. An initial finite element analysis was performed in order to identify the optimum skin to foam thickness ratio (Section 2). Then the specimens were manufactured at different thicknesses following the optimum thickness ratio and bending testing was performed (Section 3). In addition impact testing was performed at different impact energies ranging from 5J to 50J and subsequent three point bending on the impacted specimens was performed. Finally hydrostatic cycling was performed which followed pressures that reached up to 2,000 metres ocean depth. The number of cycles was believed to be equivalent to 1 year operational life of a remotely operated vehicle (ROV). The specimens were then tested under three point bending (Section 3). All the results are presented followed by the conclusions (Sections 4 and 5).

2 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

A preliminary finite element analysis was performed in order to identify the optimum skin to foam thickness ratio for maximum flexure resistance. The numerical analysis was performed with ABAQUS Version 6.12. C3D8R 8-node linear brick, reduced integration elements were used in order to model the syntactic foam core and the E-glass/epoxy resin plain weave skin. The interaction between the skin and the core was modelled as perfect contact. A uniform concentrated force equal to 30MPa was applied at the centre across the width of the upper skin of the laminate, while the out of plane displacements and rotations of the edges were constrained (Figure 1).

Figure 1. FE model for the investigation of flexural resistance (size of laminate = 150 x 40 mm, double skin), loads and boundary conditions (left) and stress distribution under bending uniform loads (right).

E-glass/epoxy skin layer	Syntactic foam
$E_1=38$ Gpa	$E=1.9$ GPa
$E_2=8.5$ GPa	$\nu=0.3$
$\nu_{12}=0.3$	$\rho=416$ kg/m ³
$G_{12}=3.5$ GPa	
$\rho=1,870$ kg/m ³	

Table 1. Material properties employed for the FE model.

The size of the laminate was 150 mm x 40 mm. The material properties used for the skin and the foam can be seen in Table 1. The skin to foam thickness ratio (t_s/t_f) was varied from 0 to 0.6 while the total thickness of the laminate was kept constant and equal to 15 mm. The maximum deflection at the centre of the laminate was recorded at each ratio and the results can be seen in Figure 2. As illustrated, the deflection keeps decreasing as the thickness ratio increases until up to around 0.15 after which no significant drop is recorded. It is therefore assumed that if the skin thickness further increases, then the contribution to the overall performance will be minimum while the skin will only increase the weight of the structure.

Figure 2. Maximum deflection of sandwich laminates at different skin (t_s) to foam (t_f) thickness ratios; results illustrate that after $r=0.15$ there is no further significant benefit from increasing the skin thickness.

3 EXPERIMENTAL SET UP

3.1 Materials and specimen preparation

The sandwich laminates were fabricated from a commercially available syntactic foam core with glass microspheres and epoxy resin, which was rated to withstand hydrostatic pressures equivalent to 2,000 metres water depth. Sandwich panels of different thicknesses were tested, following the observation derived from the FE analysis that the skin should be around 15% of the foam thickness. The skin was made of E-glass fibre fabric, plain weave twill 2/2 and followed a 0/90 stacking sequence. The size of the foam panels was 550 mm x 450 mm to allow for the cutting of several specimens. The manufacturing procedure started with the surface processing of the foam core panel, where the panel was machined to the appropriate size and the surface was sanded and cleaned for better adhesion. Then adhesive layer glue was applied on the foam surface and the lamination process took place by placing the skin layer by layer. The resin used to wet out the skin layers was Araldite LY3505 Resin mixed and Aradur 3405 Hardener. Once one side of the foam was laminated, the panel was left at room temperature for the resin to cure overnight and the other side was laminated following exactly the same procedure. Then the panel was placed in an oven and fully cured following the resin supplier curing instructions. Photo 3 illustrates the skin E-glass fabric and a representative example of a cured specimen, cut at appropriate size for three-point bending.

Figure 3. Plain weave E-glass fabric employed for the skin (left) and cured composite sandwich laminate (right).

Test	Foam thickness	Total thickness	Support span length for 3 point bending	Total length	Width
No1	6	6	128	500	30
No2	10	10	208	500	30
No3	13	13	272	500	30
No4	20	20	416	500	30

Table 2. Summary of foam specimens geometrical details for three point bending testing (in mm).

Panels at different thicknesses were manufactured and tested in order to investigate the effect of the failure modes with respect to the panel thickness increase. All panels at each thickness followed the general assumption that the skin should be no more that 15% of the foam thickness or it will add unnecessary weight without increasing considerably the overall flexural performance. Pure syntactic foams without skin were tested in addition to sandwich panels for comparison purposes. Tables 2 and 3 display the size of the pure foam and of the sandwich panels considered for 3 point bending respectively.

Test	Skin thickness	Foam thickness	Total thickness	Support span length for 3 point bending	Total length	Width
No1	1	6	8	128	500	30
No2	1.5	10	13	208	500	30
No3	2	13	17	272	500	30
No4	3	20	26	416	500	30

Table 3. Summary of composite sandwich specimens geometrical details for three point bending testing (in mm).

3.2 Bending and impact tests

Three point bending tests were conducted according to the standard ASTM D790-10. An Instron 5969 electromechanical test frame was used fitted with 10 kN load cell (Figure 4). The size of the specimens was 500 mm x 30 mm while the thickness of each configuration can be seen in Tables 2 and 3 for the pure foam and the sandwich structures respectively. The support span to depth ratio was 1:16 following the standard and details are shown in Tables 2 and 3. The three point bending load was applied at a constant rate calculated based on the followed standard. The average value of five specimens was taken in order to accurately determine the flexural parameters.

Figure 4. Three point bending (left) and impact testing set up (right).

In order to identify the residual bending strength of the impacted and hydrostatically cycled composite laminates, the bending strength of the non-impacted and non-hydrostatically cycled laminates was first estimated. Next step was the impact testing and hydrostatic testing of another set of samples which followed exactly the same geometrical specifications as illustrated in Tables 2 and 3 for comparison reasons. Then, three point bending was performed on them in order to investigate any changes compared to the bending results of the non-impacted and non-hydrostatically cycled specimens.

For the impact test, the specimens followed the same size as illustrated in Table 3. The impact testing of sandwich panels only took place since the residual strength of pure foam was not within the objectives of the current work. The specimens were subjected to the following energy levels; 5J, 10J, 20J, 30J, 50J, hence covering a wide region of energies from low to high which was expected to cause significant damage. The tests were performed using a drop-weight system, with a pair of adjustable rebound catchers to prevent any multiple impacts. The system consists of a drop tower and an impactor to which a hemispherical nose is attached. The impactor was of a 10mm hemispherical tip and 5kg mass (Figure 4). The velocity and drop height varied based on the required impact energy. The residual bending strength of the impacted specimens was statically tested under three point bending while the impacted side of the panel was pointed downwards during testing. For each geometry and impact energy one specimen was tested.

3.3 Hydrostatic cycling test

The specimens were tested in a pressure vessel with capacity of 6 litres which can reach testing pressures equal to 1,973 bars. The testing equipment consists of a tensometer controlled by a piston, pressure transducers which can reach up to 20,000 psi, a pressure pot with an operating pressure up to 1380 bars and a tube which is used in order to pump in water to the pressure pot. The tested specimen was placed inside the pressure pot, water was pumped in through the tube which was connected to the hydraulic machine, and any rapid change in the pressure was translated as failure. This change in the pressure was detected by the pressure transducers. The test followed an ASTM D2736-78 standard testing procedure while each cycle is illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Illustration of a whole cycle followed for the hydrostatic cycling test.

The hydrostatic cycling testing was designed to simulate 1 year of underwater ROV operation, equivalent to 150 cycles. Visual inspection was performed at approximately every 55 cycles. Only sandwich specimens of two thicknesses (8mm and 13mm) were tested since the others would hardly fail at these hydrostatic pressures. Three specimens were tested per configuration. The ramp up was equivalent to 1,000psi/min or 6.89MPa/min, the hold pressure was at 2,904 psi (equivalent to 2,000 metres, depth at which the syntactic foam was rated) and the relaxation ramp down was 1,000 psi/mm or 6.89MPa/min.

4 RESULTS

The damage occurred as a result of the three point bending is illustrated in Figure 6 with a representative example. The figure is of a 26mm thick composite laminate. As shown, a combination of skin fracture, skin perforation, skin delamination and core fracture take place, resulting in the final failure. Visual inspection showed that the skin carried the bending loads effectively until they reach the bending strength while at the same time the skin delaminated from the core. When the skin is debonded it is significantly fractured, and then the core eventually fails under the bending stresses. Thinner skins are more resistance to bending loads, but thicker skins require stronger adhesive layers.

Figure 6. Representative example of failure under three point bending of a 26 mm thick composite sandwich laminate (failure modes; skin fracture, skin perforation, skin delamination, core fracture).

Figure 7 presents the results of the three point bending test, of the pristine composite laminates prior to any hydrostatic cycling testing or impact testing. The same results of pure foam specimens are also presented in the same graphs for comparison. Both maximum flexural stress at which the specimens eventually fail and flexural modulus clearly show the advantage that the double skin has on the bending performance of the laminate.

Figure 7. Three-point bending results for pure foam and sandwich laminates; maximum flexural stress (left) and modulus (right).

Figure 8 illustrates the three point bending results for the sandwich laminates before and after the specimens were hydrostatically cycled for comparison reasons. The experiment was stopped at each 55 cycles and visual inspection was performed in order to identify any damage. No apparent damage was observed until the end of the cycling test. It was therefore decided that the test was limited to the thinnest sandwich laminates (namely 8mm and 13mm). It was expected that no damage would occur at the thicker laminates. The maximum flexural stress and the modulus of the cycled and non-cycled specimens illustrated negligible difference which reflects the results of the visual inspection after hydrostatic cycling which demonstrated no damage. The pressures and number of cycles these laminates were subject to are equivalent to 1 year of the operation of remotely operated vehicle (ROV) at a sea depth equal to 2,000 metres. This is a substantial depth at a significant operation life.

Figure 8. Three-point bending results for sandwich laminates; maximum flexural stress (left) and modulus (right) before and after hydrostatic cycling testing.

Photos of the impact damage caused by the different impact levels for the 17mm and 26mm sandwich laminate are illustrated in Figure 9. As shown, the damaged areas are detected on the impacted side as well as through the thickness of the laminate in the form of core fracture. The 17 mm and 26 mm sandwich laminates were the thicker laminates tested which nevertheless exhibited significant damage at high impact energies. The impact damage tends to spread as the impact energies increase.

Figure 9. Representative example of impact damage at various impact energies (5J, 10J, 20J, 30J and 50J) for the 17 mm (a), (b) and 26 mm thickness sandwich laminate (c), (d).

The force with respect to time produced during impact testing is illustrated in Figure 10 for the two laminates with thickness 17 mm and 26 mm. The smooth curve represents specimens where only the skin was damaged while the curve that exhibits nonlinear discrepancies represents failure of skin and core. In the latter case, the core was damaged because the skin was damaged at such an extent that the impact damage was spread through the skin thickness and caused core failure. Figure 10 shows that the 17 mm thick laminate suffered core fracture at 50J while the 26 mm thick laminate did not suffer any core fracture due to the thicker skin. These observations can also be seen in Figure 9.

Figure 10. Impact force with respect to time during impact testing at various impact energies (5J, 10J, 20J, 30J and 50J) for the (a) 17 mm thick laminate and the (b) 26 mm thick laminate.

The three point bending results of the laminates after impact are illustrated in Figure 11. It is important to highlight that not all specimens were tested at all impact energies. The reason for that was that some of them were completely damaged after impact, which made any subsequent bending testing needless. The 8 mm thickness laminate was tested up to 5J, the 13 mm up to 20J, the 17 mm up to 30J and the 26 mm up to 50J. This means that the 8 mm laminates tested at impact energies above 5J and the 13 mm laminates tested at impact energies above 20J catastrophically failed in the form of core fracture. The same can be observed for the 17 mm thick laminates at impact energies above 30J.

Figure 11. Maximum flexural stress with respect to impact energy for the sandwich laminates at different thicknesses (a) 8 mm (b) 13 mm (c) 17 mm and (d) 26 mm.

The results illustrate the maximum flexural stress with respect to impact energy at each laminate thickness. As observed the stress at which the laminates fail under bending for the 8 mm and 13 mm thickness drops as the impact energy increases. The drop is more substantial at the 8 mm thickness specimens where the skin thickness was only 1mm. The 17 mm thick laminates generally exhibited a behavior which cannot be related to the observed trend of the other laminates. The observed behavior does not seem to be consistent and further investigation needs to be performed. Finally the 26 mm thick laminates exhibited the same behavior with the first two laminates (8 mm and 13 mm thick), with the flexural stress dropping with respect to the impact energy.

Even though no C-scan or more in depth damage inspection was performed, Figure 12 can explain the damage mechanisms that probably took place during bending testing of the impacted specimens. As explained before, during impact, the first level of damage is the skin failure. An example of the laminate at thickness equal to 13 mm is shown. At 10J the skin is considerably damaged and it is possible that a slight skin delamination has occurred as the impact damage propagated from the skin to the core. Therefore when the laminates were subject to bending loads, the stress-strain curve produced was a linear curve which demonstrated the brittle, rapid failure with the skin not capable to restrict the propagating damage. On the other hand, at 5J the skin is less damaged and has not lost its damage carrying capabilities. This can be reflected from the stress-strain curve produced during bending test, where the developed stress drops but the laminate is still functional with the skin carrying the bending loads before it fails and the damage propagated to the core.

Figure 12. Stress strain curve produced during the three point bending of the impacted laminate at 13 mm for two different impact energies (5J and 10J).

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study focused on the investigation of the residual bending properties of composite sandwich laminates at different thicknesses (8, 13, 17 and 26 mm) made of syntactic foam and glass fibre double skin. The skin was made of E-glass fibre wetted out with epoxy resin and laminated on the two sides of syntactic foams made to withstand hydrostatic pressure of up to 2,000 metres sea water. A finite element analysis was performed which identified as the optimum skin to core thickness ratio to be 0.15. Anything above this would only add to the weight of the structure without substantially increasing the bending resistance. The specimens were tested under hydrostatic cycling loading which simulated 1 year operation life cycle of a subsea vehicle, and under impact at a range of impact energies between 5J and 50J. Specimens before and after hydrostatic and impact testing were subsequently subjected to three point bending in order to investigate the residual bending properties.

Results showed that hydrostatic testing at the chosen pressure did not have any effect on the composite sandwich and hence the bending properties before and after hydrostatic testing remained the same. This means that the hydrostatic pressures will not affect the bending performance of the laminate as long as it does not exceed the operating pressures of the syntactic foam (in this case equivalent to 2,000 metres ocean depth). On the other hand, impact showed that it can affect the bending properties of the laminates, causing skin delamination and subsequent core cracking under bending loads.

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